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**EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF ELECTRIC TOOTHBRUSHES IN
IMPROVING ORAL HYGIENE AND PREVENTING
PERIODONTAL DISEASES IN CHILDREN WITH
IMMUNODEFICIENCY DISORDERS**

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Annotation

This study evaluated the effectiveness of electric toothbrushes in improving oral hygiene and preventing periodontal diseases in children with immunodeficiency disorders and disabilities. Maintenance of adequate oral hygiene in children with limited physical or functional abilities remains a major challenge in preventive dentistry due to impaired motor coordination, reduced self-care skills, and difficulties in performing routine oral hygiene procedures. The investigation included 72 children from the Bukhara region diagnosed with periodontal diseases. Clinical dental examinations were performed to assess oral hygiene status, periodontal tissue condition, and the degree of dental plaque accumulation before initiation of preventive and therapeutic measures. The findings demonstrated that insufficient oral hygiene significantly contributes to the development and progression of periodontal inflammation and dental caries in this patient population. Mechanical plaque removal using electric toothbrushes was shown to be an accessible and effective preventive method. Modern electric toothbrushes

equipped with rotational-vibrational mechanisms and integrated timers improved the quality of plaque removal and facilitated better compliance with recommended brushing duration. Clinical observations indicated that electric toothbrushes provided higher cleaning efficiency compared with conventional manual toothbrushes, contributing to reduction of gingival inflammation and improvement of periodontal health. The study confirms the practical value of electric toothbrushes as an effective adjunctive tool in preventive dental care programs for children with immunodeficiency disorders and disabilities.

Keywords

Electric toothbrushes, oral hygiene, periodontal diseases, gingivitis, children with disabilities, immunodeficiency disorders, dental plaque, preventive dentistry, periodontal health, pediatric dentistry, gingival inflammation, plaque control.

Introduction

Effective treatment of gingivitis in children with disabilities is considered one of the priority preventive measures aimed at improving periodontal soft tissue health and reducing the risk of progression of inflammatory-destructive periodontal changes later in adulthood. Nevertheless, despite significant advances in preventive dentistry, there is still no universally accepted therapeutic, preventive, and rehabilitation protocol for patients with chronic generalized catarrhal gingivitis, largely due to the multifactorial nature of its etiological and pathogenetic mechanisms [2,4,7,9–11]. Management of periodontal diseases in children with physical or functional limitations remains a challenging issue in contemporary dental practice. Difficulties associated with inadequate oral hygiene skills, impaired motor coordination, reduced self-care ability, and limited access to specialized preventive programs contribute to increased accumulation of dental plaque and progression of inflammatory periodontal conditions in this patient population.

Aim of the Study

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the effectiveness of electric toothbrushes in improving oral hygiene and reducing dental plaque accumulation in children with disabilities.

Study Population

The study included 72 children with disabilities diagnosed with periodontal diseases who were residents of the Bukhara region. All participants underwent clinical dental examination with assessment of oral hygiene status and periodontal condition prior to initiation of preventive and therapeutic measures.

Materials and Methods

The participants underwent comprehensive clinical dental evaluation using subjective complaints, medical history assessment, and objective stomatological examination methods. Oral hygiene status, periodontal tissue condition, and the presence of dental plaque accumulation were assessed using standard clinical diagnostic criteria.

Results and Discussion

Insufficient maintenance of oral hygiene in children with disabilities is considered one of the major contributing factors in the development of periodontal diseases and dental caries. Consequently, both preventive and therapeutic strategies are primarily directed toward elimination of dental plaque and long-term control of its accumulation.

One of the most accessible and effective methods of plaque removal is mechanical cleaning with the use of an electric toothbrush. Teaching children with disabilities to correctly use electric toothbrushes plays an important role in improving daily oral hygiene practices. These devices substantially simplify routine oral care procedures and facilitate more effective plaque control compared with conventional manual toothbrushes.

Modern electric toothbrushes are commonly equipped with integrated timers designed to ensure adequate brushing duration, thereby improving the quality of plaque removal while minimizing traumatic effects on enamel and gingival tissues

[1–3,5,6,8]. Clinical observations indicate that electric toothbrushes combining rotational and vibrational movements demonstrate higher cleaning efficiency than standard manual brushes. According to published data, their use may increase plaque removal efficiency by approximately 25% and reduce the severity of gingival inflammation by nearly 10–15%.

In addition, vibrational movements generated by electric toothbrushes produce a mild massage effect on periodontal soft tissues, contributing to improved microcirculation within gingival capillaries. Enhanced blood circulation may promote reduction of inflammatory changes in periodontal tissues and improve trophic processes within the oral mucosa. Regular use of electric toothbrushes therefore represents an effective adjunctive measure in the prevention and management of inflammatory periodontal conditions in children with disabilities.

This is particularly important for adolescents, who are more susceptible to gingivitis than to many other periodontal conditions. The use of electric toothbrushes is especially valuable during childhood, as children often lack adequate brushing skills, demonstrate poor motivation toward oral hygiene procedures, or perform toothbrushing incorrectly.

Numerous investigators have reported significant advantages of electric toothbrushes over conventional manual brushes. Clinical observations demonstrated that after 1–3 months of regular use, dental plaque accumulation decreased by approximately 10–13%, while gingival inflammatory manifestations were reduced by nearly 5–7%. With prolonged use exceeding three months, reductions in plaque indices and gingival inflammation became even more pronounced, reaching nearly 20% and 10%, respectively.

Ultrasonic toothbrushes additionally generate high-frequency vibrations capable of disrupting bacterial plaque biofilm structures formed by *Streptococcus mutans*, damaging bacterial cell membranes, and impairing bacterial adhesion to the enamel surface even at a short distance from the plaque layer. These characteristics contribute to improved oral hygiene efficiency and reduction of microbial colonization within the oral cavity.

An important advantage of electric toothbrushes is their atraumatic effect on enamel and gingival tissues in both pediatric and adult patients. Their ease of use, ergonomic design, and improved cleaning efficiency make them particularly suitable for children with limited physical abilities and impaired manual dexterity.

To evaluate the clinical effectiveness of electric toothbrushes, the examined patients were divided into two treatment-preventive groups, each subsequently separated into subgroup A and subgroup B. Participants in subgroup A performed individual oral hygiene procedures using conventional manual toothbrushes. Children included in subgroup B used electric toothbrushes as part of their daily oral hygiene regimen.

Correction of oral microbiocenosis in children with disabilities plays an important role in improving the balance of pathogenic oral microflora. Facultative and obligate anaerobic microorganisms participate in the formation of dental plaque and contribute to the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases. More than 80–90% of microorganisms capable of adhering to tooth surfaces are involved in dental plaque formation. According to Shindeev and colleagues, prolonged retention of dental plaque on tooth surfaces creates favorable conditions for persistence and proliferation of pathogenic microorganisms within the oral cavity.

Anti-inflammatory toothpastes are widely used as an adjunctive measure for controlling plaque accumulation and improving oral hygiene. When adequate oral hygiene is maintained, formation of dental biofilm decreases, resulting in reduction of inflammatory manifestations within periodontal tissues. Clinical observations indicate that the concentration of chlorhexidine in such formulations may exert a bactericidal effect on pathogenic microorganisms.

In comprehensive periodontal prevention programs, various oral hygiene products are additionally used, including mouth rinses, herbal preparations, and plant-derived extracts with anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties.

Figure 2. Clinical condition of the oral cavity after the use of an electric toothbrush.

Use of both types of toothbrushes demonstrated a statistically significant positive clinical effect; however, substantially better outcomes were observed in subgroup B, where electric toothbrushes were used. All evaluated clinical parameters in this subgroup showed more pronounced improvement compared with subgroup A, in which conventional manual toothbrushes were utilized, as well as with the control group.

Significant improvement was observed in both periodontal and oral hygiene indices. In particular, the PMA index, which reflects the severity of gingival inflammation, decreased in subgroup B of the first treatment-preventive group from $19.8 \pm 1.4\%$ to $9.7 \pm 1.5\%$ following completion of the preventive-therapeutic program, representing an approximately twofold reduction. In subgroup A, the same index decreased from $22.1 \pm 2.0\%$ to $15.2 \pm 1.3\%$, corresponding to a less pronounced improvement. Comparative analysis between the subgroups demonstrated superior therapeutic effectiveness in favor of the electric toothbrush group.

The gingival bleeding intensity index also demonstrated positive dynamics after treatment in both study subgroups. Nevertheless, reduction of bleeding manifestations was more evident among children using electric toothbrushes.

Evaluation of oral hygiene indices in children with disabilities revealed a marked decrease in plaque accumulation. In subgroup A, oral hygiene indicators improved by approximately 1.4-fold, whereas in subgroup B improvement approached a twofold reduction with achievement of values close to physiological norms. This

finding indicates enhancement of oral self-cleansing mechanisms and improved maintenance of daily oral hygiene.

The obtained clinical results were additionally confirmed by laboratory investigations. Microbiological and cytological parameters demonstrated favorable dynamics during the course of preventive and therapeutic interventions, indicating reduction of inflammatory activity and normalization of oral microbial balance.

In the third treatment-preventive group, adjunctive pharmacological therapy with Asepta® gel was included in the treatment protocol. This topical preparation may be used in the management of various inflammatory and traumatic lesions of gingival tissues and oral mucosa.

The preparation may also be used for preventive purposes. One of the principal advantages of this gel is its liquid adhesive base composed of pectin. Owing to this property, the formulation is evenly distributed over the mucosal surface, gradually swells, and remains firmly fixed on the gingival tissues for up to 30 minutes within the oral cavity.

These characteristics facilitate effective penetration into difficult-to-access interdental areas, promoting more efficient elimination of pathogenic oral microflora. Simultaneously, use of the gel contributes to reduction of tooth and gingival hypersensitivity and supports long-term maintenance of satisfactory oral hygiene status.

The therapeutic efficacy of Asepta® gel is associated with the combined action of metronidazole and chlorhexidine. This combination provides broad-spectrum antimicrobial and antiseptic activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative microorganisms. Due to the presence of metronidazole, the preparation demonstrates high effectiveness against anaerobic bacteria involved in the progression of severe periodontal diseases and subsequent tooth loss.

The active components of the gel exert prolonged local effects directly within inflamed periodontal tissues, contributing to suppression of microbial activity, reduction of inflammatory manifestations, and acceleration of regenerative processes in gingival structures.

Conclusions

Hygienic and preventive measures alone did not result in complete clinical recovery in children presenting with moderate and severe forms of periodontal inflammation. Therefore, an additional treatment-preventive group consisting of children with more pronounced periodontal manifestations was formed, in which Asepta® gel was included in the therapeutic protocol according to the manufacturer's recommendations.

The second study group (control group) included children who received conventional periodontal therapy consisting of antiseptic treatment procedures and topical anti-inflammatory applications routinely used in pediatric dental practice.

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